

Tularemia: An Overview

M. M. Soni^{1*}, P. A. Anjaría¹, J. B. Nayak¹ and M. N. Brahmhatt¹

¹Department of Veterinary Public Health & Epidemiology,
Veterinary College, Kamdhenu University, Anand- 388001, India

Corresponding Author: mansisoni2707@gmail.com

Abstract

Tularemia is a zoonotic disease transmitted by direct contact, arthropod bite, ingestion of contaminated food/water, aerosol, and skin contact. It produces several symptoms in humans like lacrimation, photophobia, conjunctivitis, and in animals, it produces symptoms like ocular nasal discharge, lymphadenitis, greyish and white splenic foci, coughing, pneumonia etc. Diagnosis can be done through clinical signs, cultural characteristics, serological methods, and molecular identification. There is no way to prevent the infection completely. No vaccine against tularemia is available to the public. Laboratory workers who are at a higher risk of infection must take extra precautions to avoid infection. The disease can be prevented by wearing protective clothes, repellents, immunization, proper hygiene, and health education.

Introduction

In 1911, the first case was reported in Tulare County of California. Pahvant Valley Plague, Rabbit Fever, Deer Fly Fever, Tick Fever, France's Disease, and Ohara's Fever are some of the synonyms of this disease. It is a common zoonotic disease in turkey and throughout the world. It became a major re-emerging disease due to its association with bioterrorism in the world. Expansion in tularemia cases has resulted from global warming, war, major human travel, natural disasters, and animal migrations. The low infectious dose, easy and high dissemination with aerosols, and ability to induce fatal disease make *Francisella tularensis* a potential agent of biological warfare (Snowden *et al.*, 2021). Hence, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has classified it as a Category A – biological weapon. Tularemia's pathogenic organism has been isolated from humans and a variety of animal taxa including, birds, mammals, fishes, amphibians, protozoa, and arthropods. It is also demonstrated that the existence of this bacteria in animals without any clinical signs may signify colonization without infection.

Etiology

The etiological agent of tularemia is *Francisella tularensis* (formerly known as *Pasteurella tularensis*). It is a pleomorphic, gram-negative, non-motile, aerobic, and non-spore-forming intracellular bacterium having bipolar morphology. The cell wall is rich in fatty

acids and besieged by a semi-virulent capsule. There are recognized subspecies of *F. tularensis*, with *F. tularensis* type-A causing the most severe disease and the most frequent disease in North America. Less severe disease is associated with *F. tularensis* subsp. *holarctica* (type B) in other parts of the northern hemisphere, including widespread disease in Europe.

Transmisión

F. tularensis in humans is transmitted through the skin while handling of infected animal's tissue/blood, vector bite (such as mosquitoes, ticks, & flies), ingestion of contaminated food/ water, aerosol, and aquatic transmission. Consumption of undercooked animal tissue and water, or food which is contaminated through infected carcasses or infected people's excreta. Respiratory infections can arise while executing agricultural work such as stacking hay or mowing lawns, especially when running over diseased animals or carcasses. arthropod vectors like ticks, mosquitoes, and biting flies play an important role in the transmission of disease to humans. Person-to-person transmission has not been reported (Gürçan, 2014).

Public Health Significance

In humans, tularemia can manifest itself in a variety of ways, most of which are determined by the path the bacterium takes into the body. Tularemia may be a potentially debilitating disease, particularly when caused by *F. tularensis* subsp. *tularensis*, however many cases of illness caused by lower-virulence strains go unnoticed. The most frequent kind of tularemia is **Ulceroglandular tularemia**, which is generally caused by a bite from an arthropod vector that has previously fed on an infected animal. Some incidences of ulceroglandular tularemia in hunters and trappers develop because of handling contaminated meat, with infection through scratches or abrasions (Ellis *et al.*, 2002).

The incubation period is 3 to 6 days, after that the patient develops flu-like symptoms, namely, fever, chills, headache, and generalized aches. In the case of tick-borne disease, an ulcer developed at the lower limb and can last for several months (a disease with similar symptoms but without the appearance of an ulcer is termed glandular tularemia). Bacteria are spread from this region to regional lymph nodes through the lymphatic system. These lymph node enlargements frequently resemble the characteristic bubo associated with bubonic plague. Bacteria can spread from this site to other tissues such as the lung, spleen, liver, kidneys, central nervous system, intestine, and skeletal muscles and produces symptoms like fever, headache, swollen and painful lymph gland, chills, fatigue.

Occuloglandular tularemía affects the eye and produces symptoms like – pain, swelling, discharge from the eye, redness in the eye, light sensitivity, an ulcer in form inside the eye, tender lymph glands around the eye, and ear.

In animals, the whole spectrum of clinical symptoms is unknown. Many cases are likely to be asymptomatic. In sheep and other animals, signs of septicemia include fever, anorexia, lethargy, stiffness, increased respiration and pulse, diarrhea, coughing, and pollakiuria. Rodents and rabbits may become dull and depressed, anorectic and ataxic, with a roughened coat and a tendency to huddle. Cats have been reported to suffer from anorexia, weight loss, and vomiting. In animals, skin lesions are rarely seen. Symptoms usually last for 2 to 10 days in susceptible animals and may end in prostration and death. Susceptible species may be found dead without other symptoms.

Diagnosis

Blood tests and cultural characteristics can help to confirm the diagnosis. *F. tularensis* can be cultured from cerebrospinal fluid, blood, lymph nodes aspirates, lymphatic tissue, and swabs of ulcer tissue for proper diagnosis of infection. Media used are heart agar, glucose cystine agar, BCYE (buffered charcoal yeast extract) agar, etc. Serological tests are occasionally useful which include enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and tube agglutination. When tissue samples are available, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) procedures can also be used (Harik, 2013). MALDI-ToF mass spectrometry, a novel technology, has recently been reviewed as a helpful tool for fast identification and typing of isolated *F. tularensis* strains. The accuracy of this research is heavily reliant on the availability of mass spectrum databases. However, MALDI-ToF MS – analysis yields data that are consistent with the PCR assay.

Treatment

Streptomycin, gentamicin, doxycycline, and ciprofloxacin antibiotics are used to treat the disease. Most commonly, gentamicin intravenous (IV) therapy for 7 to 14 days, depending on the severity of the infection. Fluoroquinolones, like ciprofloxacin, can be useful for the treatment of mild disease which is most widely used in a European country (less virulent strain is common). Tetracyclines can also be used with caution while treating tularemia because they are bacteriostatic and have a high risk of recurrence after discontinuing type treatment.

Prevention and Control

- Arthropod and rodent control.
- Avoid contact with an infected animal.
- Precaution while handling or skinning potentially infected wild animals.
- Use protective gloves, masks, eyewear, laboratory coat when direct contact with infectious material is unavoidable.
- Avoid drinking contaminated water (from the stream, pond, lake). Water should be boiled if used for personal consumption or food preparation.
- Food should be protected from rodents (especially rats).
- Health education and immunization.
- In animals, avoid feeding raw rabbit meat, especially to felines.

Conclusion

Tularemia is an important disease of small mammals especially, rabbits, and is a serious human health hazard. Factors such as migratory birds, global warming play an important role in transmission. In rural areas, wear protective clothing and use repellents, as well as avoid contact with dead animals and wild animals. For the control of disease, Hygienic conditions of food and water are important, especially in a country like Turkey where the oropharyngeal form is more commonly seen. Chlorinated water and properly cooked meat and animal products prevent contamination through the digestive tract. Early diagnosis of the disease affects both the treatment and the measures to be taken to control the disease. Vector survey and investigation of hygienic control in a high-risk area will help for predicting the outbreak.

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